

Superclomeleon biosensor based assay for SLC12A3 using HEK-293 SLC12A3 OE cells

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Assay description

SuperClomeleon is a Cl^- sensitive ratiometric FRET (Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer) sensor obtained by fusing a YFP mutant (Yellow Fluorescent Protein, that is a yellow variant of the GFP with a high sensitivity towards halides) and the Cyan Fluorescent Protein (CFP, insensitive to halides) (Figure 1). Intracellular increase of Cl^- finally leads to a decrease of the FRET ratio YFP/CFP.

SLC12A3 is the thiazide-sensitive electroneutral NaCl co-transporter (NCC), it is mainly expressed in the epithelial cells of the renal distal convoluted tubule (DCT), where it is responsible for the reabsorption of 5 to 10% of filtered Na^+ and Cl^- . Chloride fluxes through SLC12A3 lead to Superclomeleon FRET signal changes that can be monitored.

Figure 1. Principal of a Superclomeleon biosensor assay. Superclomeleon is based on the coupling of CFP and YFP via a flexible peptide linker. The ratio of fluorescence emission of the YFP acceptor to that of the CFP donor depended on the concentration of potassium chloride. Chloride induced decrease in the FRET efficiency is due to a selective quenching of YFP fluorescence: YFP fluorescence was sensitive to Chloride, while it had no significant effect on the fluorescence emitted by the CFP.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC12A3 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 70-80% confluent flasks and transiently transfected with Superclomeleon biosensor expressing construct. Transfection was performed in suspension, using the Lipofectamine 2000 method following manufacturer's instruction. Cells were seeded at 20'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in complete medium and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO_2 .

Superclomeleon assay

Medium was removed, cells were washed twice with 20 μL /well of Chloride free buffer and plates analysed at Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX reader using a CFP/YFP filter (exc: 438 nm for CFP stimulation, 542nm and 483nm emissions for YFP and CFP respectively).

Tyrode Standard Buffer (130 mM Na^+ and 65 mM Cl^- as final concentration) was online injected at the plate reader.

Data analysis

Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX measurements were analysed by using the Hamamatsu software (FDSS7000EX/ μCELL software U8524-03A). Data were exported as relative FRET ratio, normalized to untreated controls (cells incubated in Cl^- free buffer and injected with Cl^- free buffer). GraphPad PRISM software (Version 8) was used to create graphs.

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC12A3
Synonyms	Thiazide-Sensitive Sodium-Chloride Cotransporter, NCC
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 12 (Sodium/Chloride Transporter)
UniProt ID	P55017
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE025B-M (HEK-SLC12A3-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

<p>Superclomeleon: Relative FRET ratio</p> <p>Relative FRET ratio (normalized to untreated control)</p> <p>quenching: ~80% quenching: ~30%</p> <p>■ 0 mM Cl- ■ 65 mM Cl-</p>	Compound name (1)	HCl
	PubChem CID	313
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Applichem, #182108.1211
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	PoC = 50% Only one concentration of Cl ⁻ was tested in these cells, transiently transfected with the Superclomeleon sensor. A slight response is also observed in wt cells, due to endogenous expression of Cl permeable channels or SLCs. Anyway, compared to wt cells in induced SLC12A3 cells we recorded a significant higher sensor fluorescence quenching, which corresponds to about 50% more Cl ⁻ influx in the target cells.

Discussion

The Superclomeleon assay for SLC12A3 showed a decreased FRET ratio in the Doxycycline induced SLC12A3 expressing cells compared to mock (WT) cell line, upon injection of 65 mM Chloride compared to 0 mM Chloride injection. FRET ratio decrease was also observed in the SLC12A3 not induced (not treated) condition, possibly due to a leakage of the system.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).